

Highway Failure and Their Maintenance

Paper Id : 19175 Submission Date : 2024-08-05 Acceptance Date : 2024-08-22 Publication Date : 2024-08-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13841719

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Chandrashekhar Kumar

H.O.D.
Civil Engineering
Department
Exalt College Of
Engineering And
Polytechnic
Bihar,India

Bijendra Kumar

Controller Of Examination
Bihar Engineering
University
Govt.Of Bihar
Patna, Bihar, India

Abstract Roads are considered as the lifeline of any country. Some of the important roles roads in India's economy are:

1. Connection to villages.
2. Communication in hilly terrain.
3. Carriers of freight and passengers complementing the railways
4. Helps agricultural development
5. Administrative convenience, etc.

Engineers have been always with open mind to adopt any material available to them for its use for the construction purposes. It is logical to see that the purpose of highway construction is to provide a firm and even surface for the carriageway or the pavement which could stand the stress caused due to number of load applications.

Keywords Highway Failure, Pavement, Withstand Load

Introduction

Introduction of Highway Engineering]

CBR method is used in designing highway in INDIA

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) method is widely used in highway design in India for several reasons:

1. **Soil Strength Assessment:** CBR provides a simple and effective way to evaluate the strength and load-bearing capacity of subgrade soils. This is crucial for determining the thickness of pavement layers.
2. **Cost-Effectiveness:** The CBR method is relatively inexpensive and requires minimal equipment, making it accessible for projects across various regions in India, including rural areas.
3. **Standardized Approach:** CBR is a standardized method, facilitating consistent design practices across different projects and regions. This helps in maintaining quality and reliability in highway construction.
4. **Adaptability:** The method can be adapted for various types of soils, making it suitable for India's diverse geological conditions.
5. **Load Prediction:** CBR values correlate well with traffic load predictions, allowing engineers to design pavements that can handle expected traffic volumes over time.
6. **Historical Data:** The use of CBR in Indian highway design has a long history, providing a wealth of data that can be used for comparative analysis and future improvements.

Overall, the CBR method is a practical and effective tool for highway design, ensuring safe and durable roadways across India's varied landscapes.

For Rapid economic, industrial & development of cultural growth of Any country, A Belter Management of transportation is very important.

For development of any country, transport system is a good play role as like import or export system, connect one state to another state, one country to Another country, so it is also called life line of world. So some important phenomena road in our country are.

1. Connection of one state to other state.
2. Road transport provides door to door service.
3. Road are used by various Means of transport like private cars, two wheelers cycle etc.
4. Communicate in Hilly region.
5. Road transport is the only means of transport that offer itself to the whole community like.

Always Engineers have been consistency with spread out mind to accept any Material obtains to them for its need for Every construction Purpose. Purpose of transport construction is to provide pavement, Railway track which could stand the different type of stress due to heavy Load.

Type of Highway Construction

1. Earthen road
2. Cement Concrete roads.
3. Bituminous road.
4. WBM road.

Mode of transportation

There are four Maser Modes of transportation are.

1. Road way & or Highway.
2. Railways.
3. Waterways.
4. Airways.

Type of Pavement

There are two types of Pavements.

1. Rigid Pavement.
2. Flexible Pavement.

Pavement Layer - A surface Layer of bitumen bounded Aggregate, several Lower of best quality Aggregate and subgrade beneath.

Flexible Pavement: - The Pavement which have very low Flexural strength and are flexible in their structural behaviour under the wheel way are called Flexible pavement.

Flexible Pavement have four Layers

1. Subgrade.
2. Sub Base course.
3. Base course.
4. Concrete Pavement.

Important fact of Flexible Pavement

1. Grain to Grain Load transfer.
2. Initial cost is low.
3. Durability is less.
4. Repair work is easy.
5. Maintenance cost is High.

Layers of Flexible Pavement

Rigid Pavement

It is are those which possess considerable flexural strength of Flexural rigidity.

A rigid Pavement derives its capacity to with stand load & from Flexural strength. The rigid Pavement has the stab Action and is capable of transmitting the Loads to wider area. The rigid Pavement does not get deformed to the shape of the lower surface as it can bridge the minor variation of lower layer.

Important fact of Rigid Pavement

1. Design is more precise.
2. It has more life.
3. Initial cost is high.
4. It needs very less Maintenance.
5. It provides good visibility at night.

Layer of Rigid Pavement has there layer

1. Sub Base course
2. Base course
3. Surface course

Rigid Pavement

Flexible Pavement

Flexible Pavement design method are Empirical or semi empirical. So important method of design of Flexible pavement are consider in road & transport construction.

1. Burmister method
2. CBR method.
3. Group index method.
4. Triaxial test technique.
5. McLeod method.

Traffic and Loading

Traffic and loading transfer to the depth and weak point of the Pavement body through different combination at Axle loading depending an the truck types.

Main approaches for considering vehicle of traffic quality which affects carriageway design.

1. Fixed Vehicle.
2. Fixed traffic.

Objective of study

Aim of highway failure and maintenance

The aim of highway failure analysis and maintenance is to ensure the safety, durability, and functionality of road networks. Here are some key objectives:

1. **Safety:** Identify and rectify hazards that could lead to accidents or damage, ensuring safe travel for all road users.
2. **Longevity:** Extend the lifespan of highway infrastructure through regular maintenance, reducing the frequency and cost of repairs.
3. **Cost Efficiency:** Optimize maintenance strategies to minimize expenditure while maximizing road performance and user satisfaction.
4. **Performance Monitoring:** Assess highway conditions to identify issues early, enabling proactive rather than reactive maintenance.
5. **User Experience:** Improve ride quality and accessibility, contributing to overall user satisfaction and encouraging the use of public roads.
6. **Resource Allocation:** Prioritize maintenance efforts based on the severity of issues, traffic volume, and funding availability.
7. **Environmental Impact:** Minimize the ecological footprint of maintenance activities and promote sustainable practices in road management.

Review of Literature

The Indian Roads Congress (IRC) Guidelines, particularly IRC 37, are critical for highway design in India. Here's an overview of its importance in a literature review:

1. **Standardization of Design Practices**

IRC 37 provides standardized methodologies for designing flexible pavements, ensuring uniformity across different projects. This is vital for achieving consistency in quality and performance.

2. Comprehensive Design Parameters

The guideline includes detailed parameters such as traffic volume, load distribution, soil characteristics, and climatic conditions. This comprehensive approach helps engineers make informed decisions tailored to specific site conditions.

3. Adaptation to Local Conditions

IRC 37 takes into account India's diverse geographical and climatic conditions. It provides design solutions that are adaptable to various soil types and traffic scenarios prevalent in different regions of the country.

4. Improved Durability and Performance

By following IRC 37, engineers can enhance the durability and longevity of highways. The guideline emphasizes the importance of appropriate material selection and design methods, which contribute to reduced maintenance costs over time.

5. Traffic Considerations

The guideline includes provisions for traffic forecasting and load considerations, enabling designers to create highways that can accommodate future traffic growth without compromising safety and performance.

6. Environmental Sustainability

IRC 37 promotes sustainable practices by encouraging the use of local materials and technologies. This not only reduces costs but also minimizes the environmental impact of highway construction.

7. Research and Development

IRC 37 is informed by ongoing research in highway engineering. It encourages the integration of new findings and innovations into design practices, fostering continuous improvement in highway infrastructure.

General Criteria

Priority of Pavement cause. say as to the update in their situation or function with respect to their Era Period. It involves a comprehensive Examination of Existing research, Practices and Advancements related to Pavement design material construction & there maintenance.

Flexible Pavement deterioration mechanism

The deterioration is due primarily to the development and growth of Microcracks in flexible Pavement Material and generally called crack initiation phase.

The various factor which cause deterioration of flexible pavement can be represented as

Analysis MSA and Different loading like class A class B class AA loading in highway design

In highway design, MSA (Million Standard Axles) is a critical factor used to quantify traffic loads over the design life of a road. It represents the cumulative effect of traffic on pavement performance, allowing engineers to estimate the necessary pavement thickness and material requirements.

Importance of MSA

Traffic Prediction: MSA helps in predicting the future traffic load, ensuring that highways can withstand expected vehicular use over time.

Pavement Design: It aids in determining the appropriate design for flexible and rigid pavements, ensuring durability and performance.

Cost Efficiency: By accurately predicting load, MSA helps optimize material use, reducing construction and maintenance costs.

Loading Classes

Different loading classes define the types of vehicles and their impact on pavement. The primary classes include:

Class A Loading:

Description: Represents light traffic, typically consisting of cars and motorcycles.

MSA Factor: Lower MSA values compared to heavier classes, indicating reduced wear on pavement.

Applications: Suitable for rural roads or areas with low traffic density.

Class B Loading:

Description: Includes medium vehicles such as light trucks and vans.

MSA Factor: Moderate MSA values, reflecting a balance between light and heavy traffic.

Applications: Often used for suburban roads and low-volume highways.

Class AA Loading:

Description: Represents heavy vehicles, primarily trucks and buses that contribute significantly to pavement stress.

MSA Factor: Higher MSA values, indicating greater impact on road infrastructure due to the weight and frequency of these vehicles.

Applications: Critical for national highways, expressways, and major urban roads.

Cement is a Binding material which has cohesive and adhesive properties in presence of water.

Basic information of cement.

Weight of cement – 50kg.

Density of cement – 1440 kg/m³

Volume of cement – 0.0347 m³

There are 3 type of grade of cement.

OPC- 33 (IS : 269-2015)

OPC- 43 (IS : 8112-1986)

OPC- 53 (IS : 12269-1987)

It provides Better strength for construction.

In recent, Dry process is consider for manufacturing process. Then temperature Range (1400 -1500 °C) and Add Gypsum amount 2 – 3 %

Chemical composition of cement.

Lime – 60 - 65% – control of soundness & strength.

Silica – 17 - 25% – Excess of its cause low selling

Alumina – 3 - 8% –Responsible for quick setting

Iron oxide – 0.5 -6% – Give colour.

Magnesia – 0.1- 4% – Give colour & Hardness.
Sulphur trioxide – 1 -3% – Makes cement sound.

Aggregate

Aggregates are the inert material basically used as a filler with binding material in the production of mortar and concrete. They give body to the concrete & occupy 70 to 80% of volume of concrete.

Type of Aggregate

1. Angular
2. Rounded
3. Flaky
4. Elongated
5. Flaky & Elongated.

Characteristics of Aggregate

Strength of Aggregate – There are different test for strength of Aggregate.

1. Impact test
2. Crushing test
3. Aggregate Abrasion value
4. Shape & size test.

Sand

1. It is a mixture of very small pieces of different rocks or minerals
2. Size of sand grains. Range in size from 0.0625 mm to 2mm in diameter,
3. Formation of sand forms the weathering of erosion of rocks, minerals, transported by wind, water etc.
4. Used on sand in construction, Land scrapping, and as a row material in various industrial process.

Bitumen

Bitumen is defined as a viscous liquid or solid, consisting essentially of Hydrocarbon and their derivatives.

Properties

Bitumen should have fluid enough at the time of mixing to coat the surfaces.

1. It should be durable.
2. It have low temperature.
3. Its nature is ductile & brittle.
4. It is obtain from crude petroleum and its colour is brown to black in colour.
5. Bitumen contain low percentage of carbon

Construction Method

Construction of Bituminous Road: -

The construction of a Bituminous Road involves several key stages

Preparation

- 1. Surveying & planning
- 2. Clearing & excavation.

Subgrade Preparation

- 1. Compaction.
- 2. Sub- base
- 3. Base course
- 4. Compaction.

Base course

- 1. Material application
- 2. Compaction

Binder course

Surface course

Finishing

Curing operation

These processes ensure that the road is durable, stable and provides a smooth driving surface.

Highway Pavement Failure

Highway Pavement failure refers to the deterioration or damage of road surface. Leading to a loss of functionality or safety. It can occur due to various factors, including environmental conditions, traffic loads, poor construction practices, or material deficiencies. Here are some common types of Pavement Failures are.

1. Rutting
2. Potholes
3. Ravelling
4. Depressions
5. Shoving
6. Bleeding
7. Base or subgrade failure

Cause of Pavement failure.

1. Traffic loads
2. Environmental condition
3. Poor construction
4. Water infiltration
5. Aging & oxidation

Prevention and maintenance

Regular inspection: - Routine monitoring can help identify early signs of Pavement distress.

Timely repairs: - Patching, sealing and overlaying can extend the life of the Pavement.

Proper drainage: - Ensuring adequate drainage Prevents water form infiltrating the Pavement layer.

Quality construction: - Using high quality materials and proper construction technique is important for long term Pavement performance.

Those maintenance factors can help in minimizing Pavement failure and extending the service life of highways.

Future scope of Highway failure & its maintenance.

The future scope of highway maintenance & add resign pavement failure participate various key trends and advance aim to improvement the safety, durability of road structure. So some must point are below.

1. Best material & technology.
2. Better guidance & maintenance method.
3. Sustenance practices.
4. Enhanced predictive maintenance.
5. Public private partnerships (PPPS)

Conclusion Bitumen test Discuss about prime coat and tack coat in highway construction

Bitumen Tests

Bitumen tests are essential for evaluating the quality and performance of bitumen used in highway construction. Here are some key tests:

Penetration Test:

Purpose: Measures the hardness or softness of bitumen.

Procedure: A standard needle is pressed into a sample of bitumen under specific conditions, and the depth of penetration is measured.

Significance: Helps classify bitumen grades and determine its suitability for various climatic conditions.

Viscosity Test:

Purpose: Assesses the flow characteristics of bitumen at different temperatures.

Procedure: Measures the resistance to flow under specified conditions.

Significance: Important for determining workability during mixing and application.

Ductility Test:

Purpose: Evaluates the elasticity and flexibility of bitumen.

Procedure: A sample is stretched at a specified rate until it breaks, measuring the distance it stretches.

Significance: Indicates how well the bitumen will perform under temperature variations.

Softening Point Test:

Purpose: Determines the temperature at which bitumen transitions from a solid to a semi-fluid state.

Procedure: A sample is heated, and the temperature at which it softens is recorded.

Significance: Helps in assessing the thermal stability of bitumen.

Flash Point Test:

Purpose: Measures the temperature at which vapours from bitumen ignite.

Procedure: A sample is heated in a controlled environment, and the temperature at ignition is noted.

The future of highway failure and there maintenances and the prevention of pavement failure will be shape by technology & advancement, sustenance practices, and the need for resilient Infrastructure.

There are different type of material for used in highway construction like soil, sand, cement, aggregate and Bitumen etc. If quality of material is good them ensure good quality of Pavement surface.

By integrating smart material & real time monitoring so highway system is more efficient & durable or environmentally friendly. These innovations will not only extend the life span of highway but also reduce the overall cost and environmental impact of maintenance activities, Highway maintenance cost be planned for rapid performance and to cause least passes disruption or hazard to traffic.

References

1. *Justo & Khanna(2011) – design of flexible pavement*
2. *Highway engineering - A.K Upadhyay*
3. *S.K Khanna (2017 edition) – Highway Engineering*
4. *L.R kadiyali (2017) - Highway Engineering*
5. *Ayyub, B.M and Popescu, C (2003) – Flexible pavement.*